

ADAPTATION OF HOUSEHOLD APPLIANCES FOR HOME AUTOMATION USING EMBEDDED DEVELOPMENT BOARDS

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ABSTRACT

The research presented is based on building a system capable of adapting simple appliances for the implementation of home automation using Embedded Development Boards. For the realization of the project, it was first necessary to program a remote communication system through a platform provided by Google company called Firebase, which integrated into a circuit with a relay allowed the control of electric current for household appliances. Finally, a HTML website was created and hosted in Firebase, so that any mobile or desktop device with access to the link could maintain control of the system. The initial test was carried out with a 9W led lamp, whose results indicated the possibility of turning it on and off remotely, through a mobile device using only the link, which has global operation as long the Esp32 and the cell phone are connected to any Wi-Fi network be it the same for both or different networks. It is important to note that the system can be expanded to all household appliances, provided that in the circuits of these are integrated relays connected to the analog-to-digital converter of the Esp32 for the control of current in the terminals and switches. In this way, we see how home automation is becoming increasingly affordable and sophisticated, projects like this show how technology can be used to improve the way we interact with our homes, making them smarter, more practical and more sustainable. With the possibility of remote control and global reach, this system brings convenience to residents, Enabling individuals to manage their devices from anywhere with internet access, as in an IoT system, where everything in their home becomes accessible, makes the concept of the "home of the future" an increasingly imminent reality.

Keywords: Home automation, Embedded Development Boards, Esp32, Firebase, Internet of Things (IoT).